

DARE UK

Semi-Automated Risk Assessment of Data Provenance and Clinical Free-text in TREs

SARA

UK Research
and Innovation

HDRUK
Health Data Research UK

ADRUK
Data-driven change

Final Project Report: SARA

Semi-Automated Risk Assessment of Data Provenance and Clinical Free-text in TREs

1. Executive Lay Summary

Data are transforming health and social care, enabling life-changing discoveries, advancing healthcare services, and improving lives. Yet health data providers face challenges in extracting and linking these complex data and safeguarding its release for research. Risk assessments are key to ensure that data access does not pose privacy risks, such as containing identifiable patient information or that patients' records are processed correctly. Current processes are ad-hoc, manual, time consuming and can prohibit data access, ultimately limiting health and social care innovation.

This project focused on delivering semi-automated tools and exploring approaches to improve two areas of risk assessment and monitoring: *Data provenance*, improving trustworthiness of data ingestion, processing and linking, making sure it is compliant for research; and *Privacy assessment*, minimising the risk of identifiable information in clinical free-text records (e.g., GP letters, discharge summaries). Public Involvement and Engagement (PIE) were central to our project by ensuring: risks were properly identified and addressed; public perspectives were embedded into our outcomes; and our methods were transparent and understandable.

The project delivered:

- a comprehensive report on our public involvement and engagement and demonstration of incorporating public views into our design for both data provenance and privacy risk understanding of clinical free-text.
- an approach to explore and understand privacy risks in clinical free-text which could be applied to future data in other TREs, along with detail on the privacy risk categories.
- a visualisation dashboard for exploring privacy risk in clinical free-text.
- an open-source framework for data provenance tracing within TREs which covers the full data production workflow.
- a front-end dashboard that allows TRE analysts, researchers, and information governance teams to inspect each step of the data workflow for quality assurance and to improve transparency in how data was produced.

Our collaborative team of TREs and academic partners developed approaches and an implementable toolkit for all health data providers across the UK, which address possible public concerns. Our tools provide significant benefits for data audit and release, with the potential to improve consistency between organisations, improve data accessibility for researchers and promote access to data that has not been feasible before.

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2. Project Outputs, Summary, Output, Impact and Alignment

2.1. Work Package 1: Public Consultation

2.1.1. Summary of the Work Package

From the outset, our ethos has been to embed Public Involvement and Engagement (PIE) as an integral element of the SARA project. As a direct reflection of this ethos, our team included a Reader in Health Data Science who was experienced in working with public stakeholders and an Engagement Manager who had a breadth of experience in engaging public groups from communication through to involvement exercises. The Public Reference Group at DataLoch (one of the project partners) was kept up-to-date with developments and they contributed to the piloting of the survey strand of the work.

2.1.2. Principle Activities & Outcomes:

Our principal activities were **two deliberative workshops** and a **survey which reached a representative sample of adults in Scotland**. Through these activities, our aim was to explore the perspectives of people across society, particularly including those who may not have had any connection or knowledge of the use of routine / administrative data for research.

Working collaboratively with Ipsos Scotland we designed and delivered two half-day in-person workshops for two different groups of participants (one hosted in Edinburgh – 22 participants, one in Aberdeen – 17 participants) – preceded by a single half-day online introduction session – to explore perspectives around risk assessment and semi-automation within health data research services. As part of the development of these workshops, the SARA team designed case study and scenario materials to form the foundation of the deliberations. These materials, along with time for questions and answers, brought all participants to the same level in terms of knowledge of data provenance and privacy risk assessment.

The survey was informed by the initial findings of the deliberative workshops and aimed to seek broader perspectives on key themes through the Ipsos KnowledgePanel UK platform. Through this we reached a representative sample of 1,030 adults in Scotland.

The key output from WP1 is a comprehensive report that combines the two consultation strands into a single publication. The key findings from the workshops reflect the nuanced understandings and deliberations of participants. With respect to free-text patient data and TRE trustworthiness, the report states:

To ensure TREs maintain confidentiality participants supported the idea of coding certain data (such as sentences that include a patient's living arrangements or relationships where there was a risk that this could be identifiable) and approaching very rare health conditions with particular caution.

While it was agreed that steps should be taken to protect patient privacy, a concern was also raised that too much information being removed or redacted from the data would negatively impact the quality and usefulness of the research. This led to a common view that the approach to maintaining confidentiality would need to take account of the research itself.

To **ensure trustworthiness in TREs**, participants recommended:

- Providing audit trails, which detail the checks made by those working in the TRE.
- Providing decision logs that detail what information has been removed, or kept in, and the reasons why.
- Ensuring researchers are adequately vetted and trained before accessing a TRE, and that the consequences for any misuse of data are clearly outlined to them.
- Ensuring there is clear communication between the analyst and researcher so that the needs of the project are well understood.

Regarding record-keeping for data provenance purposes:

To ensure a transparent process, participants recommended:

- Having a decision log as part of the dashboards, including decisions made about data included or excluded (and why).
- Having a quality standard or statement about quality procedures to show staff had followed a consistent procedure.

To maintain confidentiality, participants recommended:

- Having low numbers banded to minimise the risk of patient identifiability.
- Replacing some details – like the type of drug or the specific condition – with less specific descriptions.
- Streamlining the dashboards so that they only contain the necessary information for those involved in the research to do their jobs effectively.
- Ensuring there is clear communication between the researchers and analysts to help make decisions that balance patient privacy with relevance to the research.
- Supporting efforts to make the recording of notes (by health practitioners) more consistent.

For the role of semi-automation in data provenance and maintaining confidentiality of free-text patient data:

Participants were receptive towards semi-automation and its potential use for both record-keeping and managing free-text patient data, **but highlighted some conditions** they felt should be in place for its use to be considered acceptable:

- The computer would need to take account of differences in the data (e.g. in language) and inconsistencies (e.g. use of abbreviations).
- There should be regular random spot checks by TRE staff to ensure the semi-automation is working properly over time.
- There should be ongoing maintenance checks of the algorithms underpinning the semi-automation to ensure that it does not repeat mistakes or embed biases.
- Fundamentally, the use of semi-automation was deemed acceptable (acknowledging the benefits of scale and speed) as long as there is human involvement to interpret the nuances and make decisions.

The survey analysis supports the main findings of the workshop deliberations, especially in terms of the decision-making role to be retained by a human.

Considering how data analysts should record decisions when processing data for research use:

- **45% felt that only key decisions about the data that could identify someone should be recorded.** Over a third (38%) felt that everything should be recorded, while 11% felt that nothing should be recorded.
- **65% supported a mostly or completely automatic approach to record-keeping**, while 30% preferred a mostly or completely manual (i.e. human) approach.

Considering approaches to dealing with indirect identifiers in free-text patient data, the most preferred approaches were that:

- **The data analyst shares the information but removes indirect identifiers that are not relevant to the research (33%); or,**
- **Indirect identifiers be replaced with less specific phrases before sharing (31%).**
- 15% said the information should be shared as they are, with only direct identifiers removed, while 5% said the information should not be shared at all.

Considering the role of semi-automation in helping to find direct and indirect identifiers:

- **Preferences were fairly evenly split for the process of finding direct identifiers**, with 37% saying it should involve both data analysts and computers, but mostly computers. Almost as many (36%) felt the process should involve both, but mostly analysts.
- **For the process of finding indirect identifiers, there was slightly more of a preference for analysts, with 41% saying it should involve both computers and data analysts, but mostly analysts.** Nevertheless, over a third (37%) favoured the involvement of both, but mostly computers.

For full details behind these conclusions, please refer to the public consultation report that has been submitted alongside this report.

2.2. Work Package 2: Risk Assessment in Clinical Free-text

2.2.1. Background and Aims

It is estimated that 70 to 80% of health data is found in unstructured reports yet, most research uses structured health data. The unstructured text holds a wealth of information that often cannot be found in structured text that has potential to support innovative research. The major barrier for TREs in providing clinical free-text for research is because of privacy concerns. When clinical free-text is made available for research, then existing manual redaction and checking of identifiable information is often required which is both prohibitively expensive and time-consuming. Effective management of privacy concerns requires removing both explicit or direct identifiers like names but also appropriately managing unique and potentially disclosive information, indirect identifiers (e.g., details about family circumstances or background to a medical event). This work package focuses on privacy risk arising from indirect identifiers in clinical free-text, an area that has no previously published work. Indirect identifiers in clinical free-text are an unexplored area and our work package had three aims which we have fulfilled:

- Explore NLP based approaches to identify indirect risks
- Develop a prototype dashboard to allow visualisation and understanding of privacy risks such that it supports more effective risk assessment of clinical free-text for release.
- Understand the public perspective of using free-text, managing privacy risk in free text and how semi-automation could be used to support the management of risks and clinical free-text data release

2.2.2. Principle Activities & Outcomes:

2.2.2.1. Exploring an NLP based approach to identify indirect risks

To study indirect privacy risks, we extracted one year's worth of hospital discharge summaries, from three major hospitals in NHS Lothian, for patients with admission to a hospital ward with a >24 hours stay. We applied data pre-processing techniques to remove template information from the text such as headers and footers and sections of reports we knew would not be useful e.g., drug lists. We pre-processed reports into sentences and applied BERT Topic modelling at a sentence level, using similarity measures to cluster sentences together. We labelled the topics using class-based TF-IDF (Figure 1, an example of sentence clusters). These topic labels were manually reviewed for any that may contain privacy risks. For those that did, the sentence members of the cluster were manually reviewed as were subsequent reports. This was done across age ranges of patients, 18-30, 31-50, 51-70 and 71+.

Understanding what labels related to privacy risks. The PIE work directly influenced our approach to how we thought about what a privacy risk was when reviewing the cluster labels and reading the subsequent discharge summaries sentences and reports. Some of the sentences or mentions of things such as, ages of a patient's children, divorce, or custody on their own would not make someone identifiable but we were mindful that these were aspects the public involvement work had highlighted as sharing too much personal information and we actively included such items as part of labelling risks.

Example: Sentence-based clusters with BERTopic, topic representation generated using class-based TF-IDF

Figure 1 Example sentence-based cluster to understand privacy risk

Privacy Risks: From our review of clusters and subsequent reports we created 6 main categories of indirect privacy risks: *Unique Medical Events, Social, Locations & Organisations, Mental Health, Police, and Crime* (see Figure 2 for further descriptions of these). Often where one of these categories occur within one sentence in a report many of the other categories could subsequently be found in the report. Occurrence of risks differed across age ranges and the cumulative effect of how often a patient attended could increase the risk of identifiability. Whilst it is not surprising to find these types of categories in reports it does, however, show that care needs to be taken to consider privacy concerns beyond currently published work on direct identifiers.

2.2.2.2. A prototype dashboard to allow visualisation and understanding of privacy risks

Through a workshop, facilitated by design company *We are Rationale*, the team explored how a dashboard prototype could support Information Governance (IG) at the data release stage for de-risking free-text for use in research. The purpose of the prototype, at this stage, is to provide a visual means to explore risks present in a cohort but future use is planned to encapsulate and track the de-risk stages which incorporates the public voice that semi-automation tools should have human checks and audit trails. Our design process captured the full workflow but we have implemented only the visualising and exploring of privacy risks in the current version, with development done using R.

“Understanding the risks in new free text data or data within cohorts will help us make proportionate risk-based decisions faster.” IG Specialist

Figure 2 - Indirect Privacy Risk Categories

The dashboard tool allows for a cohort to be uploaded, assuming it has been appropriately labelled for risks. The dashboard can be used to understand the types of reports that are in the cohort, gender, age range, ethnicity, and Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD) details along with the years range of the reports. Each of these variables can be filtered to rearrange views of the data and of the risks. On the second half of the screen the risks can be viewed based on the filter selection, these are both direct and indirect risks. The report also provides a summary table of these risks which the user can drill down to individual risk types and see how these occur together in a report. The user can also view individual reports with their risk counts as well as rearrange the view to look on a per patient basis and understand cumulative risk.

Figure 3 – Example of Privacy Risk Dashboard

2.3. Work Package 3: Framework for semi-automation of data provenance tracking

2.3.1. Background and Aims

Data Analysts working in TREs must extract, pseudonymise and link together sensitive data for research within strict information governance and information security standards to protect individuals' confidentiality and privacy. However, the data processing by TREs is described as a 'black box' by researchers using this data since they are unable to see how their project data was created, nor are they able to sense-check or validate the data processing. Data Analysts must rely on time-consuming, manual checking of code and data files siloed across different parts of the TRE, which introduces the potential for errors during data processing and transfer.¹ The solution to this problem is *data provenance*, information about entities, activities, and people involved in producing data that can be used to form assessments about its quality, reliability or trustworthiness and enhance knowledge and usefulness of research outputs. This work package builds on outputs from our previous study funded by Wellcome (project ref. 219700/Z/19/Z), which explored opportunities for provenance-based metadata reporting within the Grampian Data Safe Haven (DaSH) environment. WP3 aimed to address two outstanding challenges to operationalise the provenance model in a real-world environment: (1) Co-design user interfaces for provenance data collection and visualisation; and (2) Design and implement mechanisms for collecting provenance information about the individual activities. WP3 had five deliverables which we have fulfilled and published at <https://github.com/TRE-Provenance>:

- Co-design of an interactive dashboard via interviews and a participatory design session with users to identify perspectives, preferences, and priorities
- Creation of low-fidelity designs, validated using concept walkthroughs
- Revised and expanded Safe Haven Provenance Ontology (<https://w3id.org/shp>) from practical challenges within the TRE infrastructure and the results of the user-based design
- Provenance collection and visualisation software prototype
- User validation and evaluation interviews and questionnaire

2.3.2. Principle Activities & Outcomes:

2.3.2.1. Interviews and participatory design session to co-design interactive dashboard; Creation of low-fidelity designs validated using concept walkthroughs

In order to understand how data is processed within the TRE to capture within a provenance workflow and to understand the specifications for visualising relevant information to improve openness, transparency and quality assurance a series of interviews were conducted with Data Analysts, Information Governance teams and researchers to document (1) the provenance information about individual activities and their inputs workflow as it is prepared by Data Analysts within TREs, and (2) requirements by users about what should be captured and visualised within the data provenance visualisation tool. The first allowed for the translation of the workflow into the generic PROV-O vocabulary (Agents, Activities, Entities) (see section 2.3.2.2). The second allowed the designers to create low fidelity dashboard designs based on user requirements within the project scope, addressing key needs of users in improving their ability to inspect the data as it progresses through the workflow. Dashboard designs were then validated with users to ensure fidelity to the specification. A separate report detailing the interviews, participatory design sessions, and creation and validation of low-fidelity designs is provided as a project output.

Public involvement in dashboard design. An important piece of this project was to ensure that this work package also incorporated in the views and feedback from the public to allow for openness and transparency around how their data is processed and audited within TREs. The workshop participants were provided with simplified variations of the low-fidelity designs, where they commented on the visual look and feel of the designs, but also, the content of the information they displayed. Key contributions were that they broadly supported that automation could be used to capture key information about data processing in the TRE; but they were also clear

¹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5896589/>

that there should still be human review of the automation and inspection of the data and the ability to comment on specific parts of the workflow and suggested the addition of comment boxes throughout the dashboard. A second contribution was not to colour code items 'green', as they believed this could result in this data not being inspected or reviewed in the provenance trace.

2.3.2.2. Revised and expanded Safe Haven Provenance Ontology; Provenance collection; Visualisation software prototype; User validation and evaluation

The findings from the interviews and co-design sessions also helped to formalise the data workflow within the TRE. Subsequently, the workflow could be mapped to the generic components of PROV-O, the W3C Provenance Ontology that classifies data into Agents, Activities, and Entities. We then expanded the PROV-O generic vocabulary with the TRE-specific vocabulary to formalise the Safe Haven Provenance Ontology and create knowledge graphs of the relational connections of the provenance trace (<https://w3id.org/shp>), expanding and updating the vocabulary to reflect the practical lessons learnt from the development of the provenance tracking solution in a real-world environment.

To ensure interoperability of the provenance data across the TRE ecosystem, the provenance trace is described using the RO-Crate base model (also used by TRE-FX and TELEPORT) and extended using the vocabulary from the SHP ontology which also reuses the standard W3C PROV model for documenting provenance. The role of SHP vocabulary is to provide a domain specific context of the TRE environment by describing specific types of activities, data assets, agents, etc. The approach is agnostic to the technology used to produce the provenance descriptions. However, to enable testing of a complete prototype solution we have developed a series of PowerShell scripts that automatically collect provenance information from the file system of the TRE server. The scripts process CSV files containing extracted datasets and additional metadata and produce provenance traces in JSON-LD format. The provenance traces can then be viewed in a human readable format using the prototype graphical user interface called Provenance Explorer. In addition to viewing the data, Provenance explorer executes and visualises results of a number of rule-based validation checks against the provenance trace.

An additional output is the creation of a web-based database/variable capture tool for researchers to select databases/variables for their project, with the visualisation tool linked to the SQL databases and automating this stage of data processing to improve transparency for researchers.

Once the dashboard was finalised, we validated its design and usefulness via qualitative user evaluation sessions and a post-evaluation session survey. Overall, users were positive about the dashboards helping them to easily view the data workflow, the ability to interrogate both the full workflow and each step in the data processing and that it brought together the ability to review and interrogate information in one place rather than in existing siloes; they also appreciated the automated checks whilst still being able to interrogate the data manually for additional quality assurance. Feedback from the public has been incorporated: No green 'pass' colour; highlight risks of small numbers that could potentially disclose individuals (e.g. ≤ 10 , ≤ 5); and comments capturing information about the data at each stage of processing. All of the above components can be accessed at <https://github.com/TRE-Provenance/TRE-Provenance.github.io>).

Challenges. There were a number of challenges faced in the provenance collection and dashboard creation. First, a substantial portion of the provenance trace was inferred from the creation and movement of files between folders and sub-folders (e.g. 'Import', 'Export', etc.), and not all activities performed result in a file creation. As a result, the TRE changed its folder/subfolder structure and naming conventions to improve the automated recording and classification of certain events. Second, certain steps, such as approvals/rejections of validation checks and data transfer/release signoffs, sit outside of the TRE and therefore enhanced metadata about these activities cannot be automatically captured within the TRE environment. Third, the framework prototype is currently designed for use by Data Analysts within the TRE and does not offer segmented 'views' for IG or researchers. However, the tool can certainly be used to demonstrate quality assurance to IG teams by offering a single, accessible track of the data as it progresses through the workflow; and data analysts are easily able to view any potentially disclosive fields to assess whether researchers can be shared the views. Finally, the provenance

creation will need to be customised by each TRE dependent on its own data workflows/data production (e.g. may not be file-based). However, we offer a clear methodology and open-source outputs that can be customised to individual TREs specifications, which has the potential to enable data provenance equivalencies between organisations. If implemented, this tool will improve the openness and transparency of data production across the UK TRE landscape.

dash:projectX/import/DaSH123_SMR01_Release_v1.csv

Dataset Details						
Description: In-patient hospital data capturing information throughout patient's hospital stay, diagnosis and operations performed.						
Path: file:///c:/projectX/import/DaSH123_SMR01_Release_v1.csv						
Row Count: 231						
Unique CHIs: 211						
Male/Female ratio: 49						
Validations						
Variables Violating Min Constraint (0): PASS						
Variables Violating Max Constraint (0): PASS						
Sensitive Variables Found (0): PASS						
Dataset Contains Variables Not Present in Linkage Plan (0): PASS						
Dataset Variables Statistics						
	Data Type	Min Value	Max Value	Smallest Distinct Nu...	Complete	Complete (%)
ADMISSION DATE	date	2015-08-01	2018-12-31	1	231	100
ADMISSION REASON	string	1A		1	231	100
ADMISSION TYPE	numeric	11	99	1	231	100
DATE OF MAIN OP...	date	2015-08-01	2018-12-31	1	231	100
DATE OF MAIN OP...	date	2015-08-08	2018-12-31	1	13	6
DATE OF MAIN OP...	date	2015-09-02	2018-12-31	1	2	1
DISCHARGE DATE	date	2015-08-06	2018-12-31	1	231	100
DISCHARGE TRAN...	string	00		1	231	100
DISCHARGE TYPE	string	10	11	1	231	100
DaSH123 StudyNu...	numeric	2222000001	2222000658	1	231	100
MAIN CONDITION	string	D123	Z987	1	231	100
MAIN OPERATION	string	XZ98	DC321	1	231	100
MAIN OPERATION 1	string	XZ98	DC321	1	13	6
MAIN OPERATION 2	string	XZ98	XZ98	1	2	1
OTHER CONditio...	string	D123	D123	1	210	91
OTHER CONditio...	string	D123	D123	1	183	80

Figure 2 Example of Data Provenance tool, with feedback from the public integrated

3. Impact of the SARA Project and alignment with DARE UK programme

3.1.1. WP1 Public and Patient Involvement

The headline impact of WP1 is reflected in the decisions made within the design and development of the prototype dashboards and approaches to understanding privacy risk in the other Work Packages. The fundamental contribution that our public consultation makes to the DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint relates most strongly to embodying the first Design Principle: “Public trust first, last and always. The strongest design voice should come from the ‘public persona’.”² By involving a broad sector of society through our multi-stage consultation approach, we have secured a range of perspectives on the concepts at the core of our project, and enabled these perspectives to have a direct influence on the decisions made throughout our development work.

3.1.2. WP2 Privacy Risks in Clinical free-text

The headline impact of WP2 is that we have moved beyond what is known about privacy risk and shown that indirect privacy risks do exist. We have characterised these into broad categories, such that methods of semi-automatic detection and labelling could now be applied. Through careful design of our deliberative workshops and survey we have been able to gain an understanding of public opinion in this area and embed that in our approach to understanding which data elements pose privacy risks. Having awareness of these privacy risks and an understanding of the public voice empowers TREs with knowledge to support proportionate risk-based decisions which should streamline and support easier data access. Our prototype to visualise and gather information on privacy risks in our dashboard can be built upon in the future due to its open-source coding and the design work undertaken.

² Federated Architecture Blueprint, <https://dareuk.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/DARE-UK-Federated-Architecture-1-Initial.pdf>, p.14

"Easier and more streamlined access to sensitive data is the raison d'être of the DARE UK programme and of the Federation." (Data Access: DARE blueprint¹)

Overall, this work package aligns to the federation blueprint in the vision for data accessibility, reducing access barriers (R008) and tooling for assessing data anonymity (R019). We have introduced an approach that can be used to understand risk in sensitive health data and will support future easier release by TREs of this sensitive data.

3.1.3. WP3 Data Provenance

The headline impact is that in producing the data provenance tool, we have improved the openness and transparency of data production inside the TRE so that researchers have a better understanding of how their data was produced for analysis. For Data Analysts, they are more easily able to review the data as it is processed through the workflow and are easily able to inspect the data production to undertake quality assurance. By semi-automating this process in a single, easy-to-use visualisation tool, it will improve the speed at which data can be released to researchers and provides an important audit tool for IG teams when reviewing data processing. By asking the public to review our prototype designs, we have learned significant insights into how the public felt that data provenance could be used. Like WP2, the key alignment of WP3 aligns to DARE UK's core driver to deliver the streamlined access to sensitive data. Our data provenance tool helps enable most criteria as set out in DARE UK's Federated Architecture Blueprint Master Requirements, but particularly supports Metadata standards, Transparency, Governance and Data production (including linkage). Further implementation of our framework for data provenance tracking in TREs will improve consistency and equivalency of service delivery across secure data facilities. Moreover, by using coding formats that correspond with other DARE UK driver projects (TRE-FX, TELEPORT, SACRO), we have purposefully created links to other projects in order to integrate with the push/pull of data from multiple TRE sources and to capture disclosure-checked research outputs within the provenance trace to create a full end-to-end integration of data processing for a truly federated TRE architecture.

4. Future Plans and Conclusion

The work has the potential to directly impact information governance committees and data controllers providing quality assurance mechanisms for the risk assessment process, as well as the research community by accelerating access to data with transparency about how this data has been processed prior to release. This is vitally important to support researchers in their innovative work, bringing them as close to real time data and bridging the gap to clinical use.

In the near future we plan to publicise more of our work to make other TREs aware of our project. We will do this through two planned journal publications and through conference attendance involving demos of our tools.

As we move forward, we will be looking to develop and test our approaches and tools further. This will include working with TREs who operate under different models and pull data from different sources (e.g. NHS, University, Local Authority) and improving our current tools based on further user feedback. In addition, we see a clear path to more integration of tools such as ours and tools developed in other DARE projects to realise the DARE federated aims including integrating:

- the data provenance and the clinical free-text risk assessment dashboard
- SACRO's outputs to capture researcher outputs in provenance trace.
- TRE-FX/TELEPORT to capture data ingress/egress/transfer at the dataset level, including linkage, for a full end-to-end provenance trace including the integration of privacy risk assessment of linked data sets across TREs

We look forward to further opportunities to share our tools with other TREs and integrate them with other DARE UK Driver projects.

5. Contributors & Affiliations

Arlene Casey ^{1,2} ORCID: 0000-0003-3256-0654
Amy Tilbrook ¹ ORCID 0000-0002-0294-2101
Stuart Dunbar ¹ 0009-0006-5318-3180
Pamela Linksted ¹ ORCID 0009-0006-5318-3180
Kathy Harrison ¹ ORCID 0009-0006-7435-7135
Nicholas Mills ¹ ORCID 0000-0003-0533-7991
Katherine O'Sullivan³ ORCID 0000-0002-9225-4942
Milan Markovic⁴: ORCID 0000-0002-5477-287X
Ana Ciocarlan⁴: ORCID 0000-0001-9202-7654
Katie Wilde³: ORCID 0000-0001-5024-8846
Charlie Mayor⁵ ORCID 0000-0003-4729-3536
Jacqueline Caldwell ⁶ 0000-0002-3506-2936
Elizabeth Ford⁷ ORCID 0000-0001-5613-8509

Affiliations

1 DataLoch, Usher Institute, University of Edinburgh; 2 ACRC, Usher Institute, University of Edinburgh; 3 Grampian Data Safe Haven (DasH), University of Aberdeen; University of Aberdeen; 5 West of Scotland Safe Haven, NHS Glasgow; 6 eDRIS, Public Health Scotland; 7 Brighton and Sussex Medical School, University of Sussex;